
INVESTIGATION OF RESISTANCE TO EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS: A FOCUS ON SECONDARY EDUCATION IN SOUTH EAST GEOPOLITICAL ZONE

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ABSTRACT

This research work was designed to uncover the causes of the continuous resistance to the effective utilization of the available educational materials in secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were raised for the successful conduct of the study. A sample of one thousand respondents and a set of questionnaire were used for the collection of relevant data. Mean rating and Chi-Square test were employed in data analysis. Analyzed data revealed that poor or negative attitude of secondary school teachers and poor or inadequate training of teachers are active factors militating against effective utilization of educational materials in secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Based on these factors, the researchers recommended that regular but continuous orientation, seminars, conferences and workshops should be organized by all the stake holders.

Keywords: Resistance to Utilization, Educational Materials, Secondary Education, South East Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria

Introduction

In educational setting, educational material utilization is as important as life. The positive outcome of its utilization cannot be quantified or over emphasized. The use of appropriate educational materials and facilities started with the existence of man on earth. It has been proved through researches that there cannot be a meaningful instructional process, if the effective utilization of instructional materials is neglected and abandoned

It is worth noting that in spite of the strategic roles played by effective use of available educational materials in instructions, most teachers in pre-primary, primary and secondary schools have consistently and continuously resisted the effective utilization of the available relevant instructional materials and facilities. This situation is likened to a soldier going to war without his gun or a farmer going to his farm without the essential farming tools. Certainly, no meaningful operation takes place when such people operate without the essential weapons and tools, respectively. Some educationists and educators have in no small measure, stressed the need for an effective use of available relevant instructional materials and facilities. Okorie (as cited in Emmanuel, 2018) opines that when the educational media are used properly, consistently and effectively, they can stimulate interest, help to reduce boredom, induce retention of factual ideas or concepts as students come in contact with what is taught. In a similar vein, Emmanuel (2018) strongly believes that the effective utilization of educational resources and materials to enhance effective instructional process is as important to the learners as food is important to living things. It is in full recognition of the indispensable nature of instructional materials that Onyeozu (2007) says that instructional materials are resource materials which help to facilitate teaching and learning process.

It is quite unbelievable and unthinkable to realize that, the strategic benefits of using relevant educational materials are thrown into the dust bin by teachers in the primary and secondary schools. It is true that the relevant educational materials and facilities are scarce and expensive, but it has been observed with great dismay, that there is much resistance to the effective utilization of the available materials and facilities,(Chiaka, 2008). It was based on the avoidable resistance to the use of available educational materials that the researchers decided to carry out this research work entitled Investigation of Resistance to Effective Utilization of Available Educational Materials: A Focus on Secondary Education in South East Geopolitical Zone.

Statement of the problem

The reasonable outcomes of using educational materials and facilities range from making learning interesting, attractive, and permanent to equalizing the educational opportunities to all learners.

Surprisingly, it has been observed that most teachers in secondary schools in the states in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria have undoubtedly paid deaf ears to the powerful dividends of effective utilization of available instructional resources. The uncommon reasons for dodging the use of available instructional materials cannot be easily identified without proper and serious investigation. Some teachers hold the belief that the available instructional resources are grossly inadequate and some of the resources are not tailored to the needs of the learners. Some teachers attribute the unacceptable resistance to the use of available educational aids to ignorance and lack of creativity. Thus, this category of teachers has no other choice than to abhor the use of any instructional material and facilities in their day-to-day instructional processes.

From physical but personal observations, the researchers conclude that most teachers in secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone develop poor and repulsive attitude towards the use of available educational materials and facilities. This awkward attitude towards the use of educational aids may have been caused by some unknown factors. Based on these observations and other factors, the researchers chose to embark on this present study. Their objective was to uncover the root causes of the non-stopping resistance to the effective utilization of the existing relevant educational materials, facilities and equipment.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, this study was aimed at:

- a. Finding out the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the utilization of available educational materials.
- b. Finding out the level of training, the secondary school teachers have on the effective utilization of educational materials in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The beneficiaries of the result of this study include; secondary school teachers, government and non-governmental organizations.

The result of this study will uncover the hidden factors that enhance the ceaseless resistance on the effective utilization of the available educational materials, by secondary school teachers in South East Geological Zone.

The outcome of this study will surely rekindle and boost the urge for the use of educational materials by secondary school teachers and instructors.

In no small measure, the result of this research work would attract the interest and concern of the government and non-governmental organizations in encouraging the supply and effective use of relevant educational materials and facilities.

Delimitation of the Study

This study was limited to the investigation of the resistance associated with the effective utilization of educational aids and related materials. The study covered only the secondary school teachers in all the five states of South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Research Questions

These include:

- a. What is the attitude of secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone towards the effective utilization of educational materials?
- b. To what extent are the secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone trained on the effective utilization of educational materials?

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses that guided the analysis of data include:

- a. The secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone do not have significant positive attitude towards effective utilization of the available educational materials.
- b. The teachers in the secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone do not have significant training on the use of educational materials.

Methodology

Design of the study

For this particular study, the survey design approach was adopted. The researchers investigated a group of people by selecting a sample from the entire population of the study for the purpose of providing an accurate description of the group. A set of questionnaire was used to collect the relevant data from the respondents in the sample which served to represent the entire population

Area of the Study

The research work was conducted on secondary schools in the five states in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. These include: Imo State, Ebonyi State, Abia State, Enugu State and Anambra State.

Population

The population of this study consists of all the teachers in all the public and private secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone. There are about two thousand three hundred and fifty (2,350) public and private secondary schools having about fifteen thousand and seventy (15,070) teachers in the study area.

Sample

For this study, only twenty secondary schools (public and private) were randomly selected from each of the five states of the geopolitical zone. From each selected school, only ten secondary school teachers were randomly selected from the junior secondary school section of the school. This gave a total number of one hundred (100) secondary schools and one thousand (1,000) respondents for the sample.

Sampling Technique

For the elimination of bias and other related factors, the random sampling technique was adopted in the selection of the sample of the study from the entire population. Using this approach, twenty secondary schools in each of the five states were selected. This method of random sampling was adopted in the selection of ten respondents from each selected secondary school, in all one hundred (100) secondary schools and one thousand (1000) teachers (respondents) were randomly selected.

Instrumentation

From this study, a set of questionnaire served as instrument for the collection of relevant data. The instrument was designed for the serving teachers in the secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone. The questionnaire has eighteen (18) items and each item has four-point modified Likert type options, namely: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree.

Validity of Instrument

The instrument was presented to seasoned experts on Research Methods, Measurement and Evaluation and Educational Technology in Federal College of Education, Obudu. The corrections and inputs from these experts helped to establish the face and content validity of the instrument.

Reliability

A pilot study was carried out on fifty (50) secondary school teachers in junior secondary school section. The teachers were randomly selected from ten secondary schools outside the sample but within the target population for the study.

Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents and after a period of two weeks, the same set of questionnaire was re-administered to the same respondents during the pilot study. The two sets of data were collected and compared using the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Technique to determine the coefficient of reliability. The calculated coefficient of reliability was found to be 0.8357, thus the instrument was reliable

Procedure for Data Collection and Data Analysis

The researchers personally administered one thousand (1,000) copies of the questionnaire to the respondents and some serving teachers were used as research assistants. A total of nine hundred and ninety-two (992) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, giving a return-rate of 99.2%. Mean rating was used to analyze the research questions, using cut-off point, 2.50 for decision taking. The research hypotheses were tested using Chi-Square Test at .05 significance level.

Data Analysis and Findings

First Research Question

Total mean is 23.0 and grand mean is 2.30. Grand mean is lower than cut-off mark of 2.50. Thus, it is rejected, meaning that the attitude of the secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone towards utilization of educational materials is negative.

Second Research Question

Total mean is 18.49 and grand mean is 2.31. The grand mean is less than cut-off mark of 2.50. Therefore, it is rejected. This implies that the teachers in secondary schools in the South East Geopolitical Zone are not properly trained on the use of educational materials.

First Research Hypothesis

OBSERVED AND EXPECTED FREQUENCIES ON ATTITUDES ON UTILIZATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
1	I very much know the meaning of instructional resources	230(171.6)	480(238.4)	277(284.2)	5(297.8)
2	I do not fail to utilize the available instructional resources in all my lessons.	79(50.0)	211(3.11)	382(33.7)	320(1.65)
3	My religion does not permit the use of any type of instructional resources in teaching.	10(152.2)	81(103.9)	296(0.49)	605(316.9)
4	Some of the teachers in my school utilize instructional materials only when school inspectors and principal are present.	606(1099.7)	300(15.9)	69(163.0)	17(264.8)
5	I have vested interest in the use of instructional materials	126(12.1)	255(1.2)	399(46.4)	212(24.7)
6	The use of instructional materials and facilities is not desirable because it wastes time and resources.	282(43.5)	430(154.0)	103(115.5)	177(49.0)
7	I strongly do not believe that the use of instructional resources has any positive impact on the academic performance of the students.	133(8.7)	159(26.4)	187(32.2)	513(160.9)

8	The use of any instructional resource should be limited to practical lessons only.	80(48.9)	112(67.0)	356(181.1)	444(71.9)
9	The use of instructional resources should not be applied to only junior secondary school students	124(13.2)	351(53.2)	493(153.4)	24(251.7)
10	The use of instructional resources should be limited to only female teachers.	46(91.9)	5(225.5)	280(0.06)	661(443.0)
		1716	2384	2842	2978

$\alpha = .05$ $df=27$ $N=992$
 Calculated value $=X^2_{cal} = 28.58$
 Critical value $=X^2_{cr} = 40.113$
 $X^2_{cal} < X^2_{cr}$ Therefore H_0 is accepted

Conclusion. Null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone do not have significant positive attitude towards effective utilization of the available educational materials.

Second Research Hypothesis

OBSERVED AND EXPECTED FREQUENCIES ON THE LEVEL OF TRAINING ON UTILIZATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
11	Most teachers in my school have special basic training on the use of instructional resources	73(180.8)	24(238.1)	282(308.4)	613(264.8)
12	I am adequately trained on Educational Technology	90(45.6)	10(218.5)	590(257.1)	302(5.2)
13	I did enough courses on the use of instructional resources in teaching, when I was in the teacher training college	18(146.6)	93(88.4)	153(78.3)	728(810.3)
14	At regular intervals, the government through the Ministry of Education organizes workshop on the use of instructional resources in teaching	82(54.0)	259(1.83)	440(56.2)	211(10.9)
15	The training I have on the use of relevant instructional materials cannot enable me teach in the secondary schools	356(169.8)	331(36.2)	252(10.3)	53(1697.7)
16	Only the permanent teachers undergo special training on the use of instructional materials and facilities	399(263.3)	300(161.1)	257(8.6)	36(197.7)
17	Only experts from civilized countries can train the teachers on utilization of instructional resources	227(11.8)	371(74.2)	344(4.1)	50(174.2)
18	Training and re-training on the use of relevant instructional resources are rarely carried out because of their expensive nature	201(2.3)	517(326.7)	149(82.4)	125(73.8)
		1446	1905	2467	2118

$\alpha = .05$ $df=21$ $N=992$
 Calculated value $=X^2_{cal} = 30.69$
 Critical value $= X^2_{cr} = 32.671$ $X^2_{cal} < X^2_{cr}$ Therefore H_0 is accepted.

Conclusion: Null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone do not have significant training on the effective utilization of educational materials.

Principal Findings

Analyzed data revealed that:

- The attitude of secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone towards the effective utilization of education materials is significantly negative.
- Teachers in secondary schools in South East Geopolitical Zone are not significantly trained on the effective utilization of available educational materials and facilities.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of the analysis of relevant data, it was observed that the first research question and first research hypothesis are in agreement. It was discovered that the overall attitude of the teachers in the South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria is significantly negative. This conclusion was confirmed as a fall out of the testing of the first research hypothesis, in which calculated Chi-Square value is less than the critical value. Thus the null hypothesis (Ho) was accepted.

The finding of this study is in line with Abibang (2008) who observed that teachers may fear the possibility of losing their act and professional privacy when they embark on the use of instructional resources. As a result, the teachers rarely give attention to the use of the available instructional resources. Olumba and Olumba(2021), discovered from their study on effective utilization of instructional materials that most teachers in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria have developed lukewarm attitude towards the utilization of available instructional media especially the high technology media, such as computer, television, projectors, etc. One can comfortably conclude that those teachers who evade the use of educational materials and facilities perceive technological advancement in education as a force that may invade the teacher's competence in any educational setting and so they abhor their effective use.

There is synergy between the second research question and the second research hypothesis. In testing the second research hypothesis, analyzed data showed that calculated Chi-Square value is less than the critical Chi-Square value. Thus the null hypothesis (Ho) was accepted. This implies that the secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria do not have significant training on the effective utilization of educational materials.

This finding agrees with the thinking of Wong in Tyozua (2017), that many of the current graduate teachers have been found to be lacking creativity, communication skills, analytical and critical thinking and problem solving skills. In a similar vein, Neo(2009) and Chiaka (2008) opined that non-utilization of instructional materials result from inadequacy of professional knowledge in the subjects. More so, Undie (2009) said that most teachers in Nigerian schools avoid the use of instructional materials due to paucity of ideas and lack of professional know-how. Undoubtedly, it can be said that the continuous hindrances and resistance to effective utilization of available educational aids can be linked to ignorance, which is the product of inadequate training on the job.

Conclusion

It is quite evident that the continuous resistance to effective utilization of the available relevant instructional materials, facilities and equipment can be properly attributed to poor or negative attitude of the serving secondary school teachers in South East Geopolitical Zone. In

addition, this unacceptable resistance to the use of available educational materials is also caused by poor or inadequate training on the part of the teachers in our secondary schools.

In no small dimension, this aforementioned resistance to the use of educational materials may have serious negative impact on the entire instructional process.

Recommendations

It is crystal clear that effective utilization of educational resources is synonymous with effective instructional process. Thus, there is much need to proffer solutions to the resistance to the utilization of available educational materials and facilities. Based on the findings of this study arising from data analysis, the following recommendations have been floated:

1. The teachers, instructors and students in secondary schools need adequate sensitization for them to realize the crucial roles played by educational media in any instructional process.
2. Continuous orientation should be mounted by educational technologists, so as to overcome the phobia and inertia exhibited by teachers and potential users of instructional materials in schools.
3. Regular but intensive conferences, seminars and workshops should be organized by the State and Federal Ministries of Education on the strategies for effective utilization of instructional resources.
4. As a motivating factor, promotion of teachers at all levels of learning should be based on their competency in the use of instructional resources.
5. Educational Technology centres should be created and fully equipped in every local government area of Nigeria. This is to make provision for regular training and re-training of teachers on the use of educational resources. Also, these centres will create access to the modern but state-of-the-art educational resources.

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COMMENDATION

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